

Online Zoning-Based Admission Systems in Junior High Schools: A Study on Efficiency and Accessibility in Gorontalo City

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to analyse and describe the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) service through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City with a focus on (1) goal achievement, (2) integration, and (3) adaptation. This research method is descriptive qualitative. Data collection techniques through interviews, observation, and documentary. Data analysis techniques through data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that (1) the achievement of goals in the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) service through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has not been effective because it still faces obstacles such as student domicile data that is not always accurate in the system, and community dissatisfaction (parents and prospective students) with online PPDB services. (2) Integration in online New Learner Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has not been effective because it still faces obstacles such as limited training for school operators and teachers, lack of public understanding, especially parents of students about zoning rules, and technical problems with network infrastructure capacity that still needs to be improved. (3) Adaptation to online New Learner Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has not been effective because it still faces obstacles in the form of unstable school internet accessibility. Suggestions to improve the success of zoning-based online PPDB services in Gorontalo City include strengthening student domicile data validation, improving operator and teacher training, socialising zoning rules to parents more effectively, and increasing network infrastructure capacity.

KEYWORDS: Effectiveness, New Student Admission, Service, Zoning System

INTRODUCTION

Public Administration, especially in the field of Education, is the science and art of managing the affairs of state and society that provides a framework for designing and managing public services in the field of Education, including the Admission of New Learners (PPDB). The New Learner Admission (PPDB) process is one form of public service provided by the government in the field of education. The aim is to provide fair and equitable access to education for the entire community. The New Learner Admission (PPDB) system, especially the online-based one, becomes a testing ground for the extent to which the government is able to apply the principles of good public administration. The successful implementation of PPDB will reflect the quality of governance.

The New Learner Admission (PPDB) online system is an activity of accepting new student candidates who meet certain requirements to obtain education at the level of a higher education unit with an online system. In other words, the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) system is a system designed to automate the selection of new learners, starting from the registration process, the selection process to the announcement of selection results, which is carried out online and based on real time (onlinerealtime) (<http://produk.siap-online.com/sekilassiap-ppdb>). The online system is a series of processes of the New Learner Admission (PPDB) online system starting from registration to the announcement of selection results which are managed automatically with a computerised system and can be seen at any time (realtime) on the website (page) and based on real time (realtime).

The main reference for online New Learner Admission (PPDB) is the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 44 of 2019 concerning New Learner Admission at Kindergartens, Elementary Schools, Junior High Schools, Senior High Schools, and Vocational High Schools, which was later replaced by the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 1 of 2021 concerning New Learner Admission at Kindergartens, Elementary Schools, Junior High Schools, Senior High Schools, and Vocational High Schools. The stipulated regulation uses a fully online system.

The implementation of an online New Learner Admission (PPDB) system in Indonesia has shown promising results in improving the efficiency and transparency of the new student admission process. Various studies have shown that online admission systems can provide faster, more orderly, and more accountable services to the public [1]. This system has been proven effective in ensuring fair admissions, reducing the risk of manipulation, and encouraging ICT literacy among the community [1][2]. The online New Learner Admission (PPDB) process usually includes the registration, selection, and announcement stages, all of which are conducted electronically [3]. While this system has generally been well received, there are still some challenges faced, such as the need for increased bandwidth, better operator training, and more comprehensive socialisation to parents and students. Addressing these issues can improve the effectiveness of online New Learner Admission (PPDB) implementation in Indonesian schools [2][4].

Online New Learner Admission (PPDB) services have also been conducted in Gorontalo City. The education units participating in online PPDB in Gorontalo City are public elementary schools, public junior high schools, public senior high schools, and public vocational high schools in accordance with the provisions regulated by technical guidelines by the Gorontalo City Education Office. The purpose of holding online New Student Admission (PPDB) in Gorontalo City is to ensure the implementation of a transparent, fair, honest and accountable new student admission system.

The number of prospective students in the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) accepted through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City in the last three years has generally increased. Online New Learner Admission (PPDB) at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City aims to provide services for school-age children/graduates to enter junior high school education units in an orderly, directed, and quality manner (<https://www.rri.co.id/ipitek/746836/>). However, in reality there are still problems in the service of online New Learner Admission (PPDB) through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City. Based on preliminary data, it is known that the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) service through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has not been fully effective (<https://hargo.co.id/berita/>). Several problems in online New Learner Admission (PPDB) often arise through the zoning system (<https://hargo.co.id/>).

A number of parents and guardians of students questioned the implementation of the Zoning pathway for new student admissions (PPDB). This is because a number of students who applied to SMA Negeri 1 Gorontalo Gorontalo City did not pass. In fact, the school is located in the Ipilo village area. Based on the data, out of 309 students who registered through the Zoning pathway, 302 passed. Meanwhile, 7 applicants were declared not passed. This incident has happened repeatedly. It has even been in the spotlight and a hearing was held at the Gorontalo Provincial DPRD. This had a very negative impact on prospective students who did not pass the zoning route, many did not pass and lost their enthusiasm for school (<https://hargo.co.id/berita/>).

The implementation of the zoning system in the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) service at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City is less flexible, causing many prospective students to be unable to enter the desired school, especially for those who live in areas with a limited number of schools. The quota is still not in accordance with the number of prospective learners, leading to disappointment. In other words, the target of the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) service in the form of a concrete target is still not satisfying the community. The online New Learner Admission (PPDB) service at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City is still faced with a lack of transparency in the selection process in the form of a lack of information publication where information about selection criteria, quotas, and selection results are often not published transparently and easily accessible to the public. There are still people or parents who suspect the possibility of KKN practices in the selection process, leading to distrust of the system (<https://hargo.co.id/berita/>).

Standardisation of procedures has not yet been achieved, with new verifiers having different procedures for registering and verifying data. This is due to the lack of socialisation about the procedures that have been determined, especially regarding the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 1 of 2021 concerning Acceptance of New Learners at Kindergartens, Elementary Schools, Junior High Schools, Senior High Schools, and Vocational High Schools.

The online New Learner Admission (PPDB) service at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City still faces several main problems, namely the problem of human resources that are not optimal with a lack of competence because not all officers, especially new officers involved in the online New Learner Admission (PPDB) process, have adequate competence, especially in the field of information technology. In addition, the high workload, namely the large number of applicants, causes officers to be overwhelmed, which has an impact on service quality (<https://hargo.co.id/berita/>). Not all families in Gorontalo City have equal access to information technology. This causes many prospective students to be left behind and unable to follow the online registration process. The uneven quality of the internet network throughout Gorontalo City is an obstacle, especially for those who live in remote areas. There are still many

parents and prospective students who are not used to using digital devices such as computers or smartphones. In addition, online registration procedures are considered complicated, making it difficult for people to follow the steps.

METHOD

This research method is descriptive qualitative. Data collection techniques include interviews, observations, and documentation. Interviews were conducted with the Head of the Gorontalo City Education Office, platform providers, school operators, teachers, parents, and technical students. Data analysis employed the Miles and Huberman model, which involves data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing.

RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Achieving Objectives in the Effectiveness of Online New Student Admission (PPDB) Services through the Zoning System at Junior High School Level in Gorontalo City

Achieving objectives refers to the overall efforts to accomplish goals as an integral process of online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City. The objectives are measured based on the quantitative achievements of the zoning system, namely the extent to which the implementation of online PPDB through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has met the target number of students admitted according to each school's capacity. The implementation of online PPDB with the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has significantly achieved the target number of students in line with each school's capacity, fulfilling 50% of the admission quota.

The main obstacle in providing online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City lies in inaccurate address validation. This validation is a crucial process to ensure that the system truly prioritizes student admission based on residence location according to zoning policies. However, challenges arise, such as the use of false addresses by parents. Some parents register their children at specific schools, particularly those considered superior, by using the addresses of relatives or family members closer to the desired schools, even though their actual residence is outside the designated zone.

Objective achievement is also assessed by evaluating whether the outcomes of online PPDB align with the goal of equal access to education. This entails whether the online PPDB through the zoning system has prioritized student admission based on residence location as intended by the zoning policy. The online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City have generally aligned with the primary objective of the zoning policy: prioritizing student admission based on residence location. This system is designed to bring students closer to schools within their residential zones. The 2024 online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City have demonstrated success in prioritizing student admission based on residence location.

To further measure the effectiveness of zoning in achieving the objective of equitable education quality, the system's ability to reduce educational disparities between regions in Gorontalo City is examined. The online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City have contributed to reducing educational disparities between regions. Based on researchers' observations, student distribution through the zoning system has successfully balanced registrants. The 2024 online PPDB data for junior high schools in Gorontalo City show that approximately 85% of junior high school students were admitted to schools within their nearest zone.

To assess technical success as part of the system's objectives, the efficiency and lack of significant technical obstacles in implementing online PPDB by schools in Gorontalo City are evaluated. Generally, schools in Gorontalo City have successfully conducted online PPDB services with good efficiency. The system is designed to enhance transparency, accuracy, and accessibility in student admissions. However, technical issues such as user surges during the early days of registration did occur but were quickly resolved by the system provider.

To illustrate the success of PPDB from the perspective of service recipients as a measure of objective achievement, the satisfaction of parents and students with the results of online PPDB through the zoning system at the junior high school level is assessed. Parent and student satisfaction with online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City varies. Most are satisfied due to the system's transparency, ease of accessing information, and simplicity in registration. However, some parents expressed dissatisfaction because their children were not admitted to their preferred schools despite being in the designated zone, especially in favored schools with limited capacity.

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that the online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City have achieved most of their main objectives, such as meeting the target number of students admitted according to each school's capacity, prioritizing student admission based on residence location, reducing educational disparities, and efficiently conducting the online PPDB process. However, challenges remain, such as domicile data in the online PPDB system not reflecting students' actual addresses, and a segment of society perceives dissatisfaction with the online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City.

B. Integration in the Effectiveness of Online New Student Admission (PPDB) Services through the Zoning System at the Junior High School Level in Gorontalo City

Integration in the online New Student Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City refers to the assessment of an organization's ability to conduct socialization, build consensus, and establish communication with various other organizations. Integration involves the process of socialization and is evaluated based on inter-agency collaboration to ensure the smooth implementation of the PPDB system. This includes coordination between the Department of Education, schools, and technology platform providers in supporting the implementation of online PPDB through the zoning system. Coordination among these parties in Gorontalo City has been effective, with the Department of Education providing clear information to the public through various media and conducting regular monitoring during the process. Technology providers have supported the development of a transparent and efficient PPDB system and provided technical training to school staff. Feedback from schools regarding technical and policy issues has been promptly addressed by the Department of Education and technology providers to improve implementation quality.

Integration is also measured by the alignment of understanding and implementation of policies among schools, specifically the extent to which the policies and procedures for online PPDB through the zoning system have been understood and consistently implemented by schools in Gorontalo City. The zoning-based online PPDB policies and procedures have been well understood and executed by schools. Most schools comprehend the zoning objectives, including prioritizing students based on proximity to their residences. The online platform ensures transparency in the selection process and admission results. Registrations that do not comply with the zone or exceed quotas are automatically rejected by the system. School operators have received technical training that enables them to manage registrations, verify data, and address technical issues, ensuring that the PPDB process runs smoothly in accordance with established policies.

To assess the effectiveness of communication in fostering service integration, it is evaluated whether communication among schools, the Department of Education, and the community (parents) during the implementation of online PPDB through zoning has been effective. Communication among junior high schools in Gorontalo City, the Gorontalo City Department of Education, and the community has been relatively effective through various socialization media and helpdesk services. Schools have established help centers, phone lines, and online media to assist the community in resolving issues during the registration process. However, despite effective communication, some parents still lack a complete understanding of zoning rules, such as distance criteria and registration priorities, leading to occasional misunderstandings and complaints about the selection results.

Further assessment of integration from the clarity and transparency of procedures in building trust involves examining the perceptions of teachers, operators, and parents regarding the clarity of rules and transparency in online PPDB services through zoning. The rules and system of online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City are generally understood and considered transparent. Most informants understand the rules of online PPDB through the zoning system. Socialization efforts by the Department of Education through social media, official websites, school help centers, and written guidelines have helped stakeholders comprehend the registration process. However, certain specific rules, such as domicile verification procedures and handling of out-of-zone students, require additional clarification. The online PPDB system is deemed transparent, as registration data, residential zones, and selection results are openly accessible to the public and schools. Automated selection features ensure a fairer and more reliable process compared to previous manual systems.

To evaluate the integration of technology systems in supporting centralized data management, the extent to which the technology platform used for online PPDB through the zoning system integrates data and information from various schools in Gorontalo City accurately and efficiently is analyzed. The technology platform used for online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has positively contributed to the new student admission process. It efficiently integrates

data and information from various junior high schools in Gorontalo City. Key data such as school capacity, the number of registrants, and admission status can be directly accessed, supporting more structured monitoring by schools and the Gorontalo City Department of Education. Automated system processes ensure selection based on zoning, age, and other criteria without manual intervention, minimizing errors or fraud. This technology-based system speeds up student selection and registration by eliminating time-consuming manual procedures.

Based on research findings, the integration aspect highlights that the technology platform for online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has successfully centralized data integration efficiently. The system supports transparency with real-time updates on school capacity, the number of registrants, and admission status, accessible by schools, the Department of Education, and the community. Automated selection processes based on zoning, age, and other criteria accelerate decision-making and reduce human errors. This system is supported by effective collaboration among the Gorontalo City Department of Education, schools, and PT Telkom Indonesia as the technology provider. Challenges in integration include limited training for school operators and teachers, as well as parents' lack of understanding of zoning rules. Technically, issues such as slow system access during peak registration times due to high traffic, suboptimal network infrastructure capacity, and inefficient data correction features were identified as obstacles.

C. Adaptation in the Effectiveness of Online New Student Admission (PPDB) Services through the Zoning System at the Junior High School Level in Gorontalo City

Adaptation in online New Student Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City refers to the organization's ability to adjust to its environment. Adaptation is assessed based on the system's ability to respond to the technical needs of the local community, such as internet accessibility and technological literacy. The online PPDB system in Gorontalo City has been designed to accommodate community needs. Free internet facilities are provided at PPDB assistance centers, hotspots in schools, and public service centers to improve accessibility. Help desks in schools assist parents less familiar with technology, while teachers and school staff are trained to provide direct guidance on using the online PPDB system. The platform features a simple user interface to facilitate usage, and text- and video-based guides are available to further educate parents and students on the registration process. However, challenges remain, including unstable internet access and limited understanding of technological applications among some community members.

Adaptation is also evaluated by examining how the zoning policy addresses challenges related to geographically remote areas, such as accommodating students living in border regions or areas with limited access within Gorontalo City. Collaborative efforts between the government and schools in implementing the online PPDB system aim to ensure equitable access to education. The zoning policy strives to provide students with opportunities to access education at the nearest schools. Schools actively disseminate information about the zoning policy and registration procedures to the community, promoting transparency and reducing misunderstandings while increasing public participation.

The system's adaptability to unexpected situations is assessed by evaluating whether the online PPDB organizers can responsively handle fluctuations in the number of registrants or technical issues. The online PPDB services in Gorontalo City have demonstrated a good level of responsiveness to technical challenges during the registration process. The system is well-designed to provide efficient and responsive services, especially in addressing technical problems that may arise.

Furthermore, the adaptability of the system to meet the needs of vulnerable groups is examined by assessing how the zoning system accommodates students from underprivileged families or those with limited access to technology. The zoning policy is designed to ensure equal opportunities for all students, including those from low-income families, to participate in the PPDB process, even with technological or internet access limitations. Online PPDB services have shown significant attention to inclusivity and equity, particularly for students from underprivileged backgrounds or those facing technological constraints. Assistance centers and mentoring programs have been instrumental in making the registration process fairer and more accessible for these groups.

To measure the system's ability to learn and adapt from previous experiences, the evaluation and improvement of online PPDB services in response to challenges or community feedback are considered. The PPDB operators in Gorontalo City have shown openness to feedback from various stakeholders, including parents, students, and schools. Concrete actions, such as increasing server capacity, demonstrate the responsiveness of PPDB implementers to technical needs. The annual adaptation and improvement

process reflects a feedback loop mechanism aimed at enhancing system efficiency. As a result, the PPDB system has become more efficient and responsive to community needs over time.

Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that the online PPDB system in Gorontalo City has been designed with sufficient flexibility to meet community needs. The zoning policy ensures equal opportunities for all students, including those from underprivileged families, to participate in the PPDB process despite technological or internet access limitations. Schools and the Department of Education provide clear and accessible information channels, such as social media publications, the official PPDB website, and public announcements. The high level of responsiveness demonstrated by PPDB organizers in addressing technical challenges during the registration process reflects the system's adaptability. However, challenges remain, including unstable internet access in school environments and limited understanding of technological applications among some community members.

DISCUSSION

A. Achieving Objectives in the Effectiveness of Online New Student Admission (PPDB) Services through the Zoning System at the Junior High School Level in Gorontalo City

Effectiveness indicators are essential tools for measuring the success of a program or policy. These indicators can be assessed through three main dimensions, the first being the achievement of objectives. Objective achievement refers to the extent to which the expected outcomes of a program have been realized [5]. It reflects how effectively an organization or program fulfills its predetermined goals, meeting planned needs and expectations [6]. In the context of research on online New Student Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City, this analysis relates closely to the concept of objective achievement.

Firstly, based on the research, the zoning system successfully met its primary targets, including: achieving the number of students admitted according to school capacity and prioritizing student admission based on residential location. This demonstrates the effectiveness of goal achievement aligned with the principle of focusing on desired outcomes [5]. Secondly, the results show that the zoning system contributes to reducing educational disparities, aligning with the objective's focus on societal impact. This indicates that the social objectives of the zoning system have been met. Thirdly, efficiency in achieving goals is crucial. The success of online PPDB services in Gorontalo City demonstrates a balance between resources used and results obtained, consistent with the framework of goal achievement.

The findings show that the online PPDB services through the zoning system have achieved most of their main objectives, aligning with the concept of goal achievement. Success is evident in achieving primary targets, contributing to educational equity, and ensuring process efficiency. According to the theory of goal achievement, an organization or program is deemed successful when its primary objectives are effectively and efficiently realized. However, goal achievement is also influenced by challenges or obstacles encountered during implementation [5]. In this context, the following relates to the theory of effectiveness that achieving goals depends on the accuracy of information and processes supporting it [5]. Issues with domicile data that do not reflect actual addresses highlight weaknesses in the input data for the PPDB system. This hampers the effectiveness of prioritizing student admission based on residential location, creating barriers to achieving primary objectives that need urgent resolution. Community dissatisfaction with PPDB services reflects that while most technical goals have been achieved, non-technical goals like stakeholder satisfaction remain unmet. Success in achieving goals also involves acceptance and satisfaction from affected stakeholders, indicating a need for evaluation in the public service dimension [5]. Efficiency in the online PPDB process, a key objective, can be disrupted by data issues and community perceptions. Addressing these implementation challenges is crucial for the organization to achieve its goals efficiently [5].

In this case, technical successes in online PPDB are less optimal if administrative and social obstacles persist. Despite positive results in several aspects, such as achieving admission targets and reducing educational disparities, the challenges of inaccurate domicile data and public dissatisfaction hinder full realization of the objectives. To enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of goal achievement, improvements are needed in data management systems and service quality to meet community expectations. The researchers suggest that the Gorontalo City Education Office develop an integrated system involving the Department of Education, schools, and civil registration services to ensure zoning data accuracy. Collaborating with related agencies, such as the Population and Civil Registration Office, for domicile data verification and validation would help align student addresses with official documents. Enhancing data security systems would also prevent manipulation by irresponsible parties.

The New Public Service (NPS) framework emphasizes a citizen-centered approach, advocating a humanistic perspective in public administration, focusing on collective responsibility and shared interests over individual preferences [7]. In the context of online PPDB with the zoning system, this approach is reflected in policies designed to ensure fair and equitable access to education for all students, particularly those residing near schools. Zoning aims to address collective community needs rather than individual preferences, embodying the spirit of citizen-centered governance.

NPS promotes humanistic values, relevant in implementing the zoning system, which seeks to reduce social inequality by prioritizing students based on their geographic location. Adjustments to the system, such as affirmative policies for underprivileged groups, reflect attention to the humanistic aspects of educational administration.

The zoning policy for PPDB represents the Gorontalo City Government's collective responsibility to improve educational equity. Consistent with NPS, this policy prioritizes shared interests over individual choices. Zoning encourages collaboration among the community and stakeholders to understand policy objectives and support its implementation, fostering collective responsibility for equitable educational outcomes.

Research by Soselisa & Puturuhi [7] emphasizes public participation as a key element of NPS. The implementation of the zoning system in Gorontalo demonstrates government efforts to involve the community through socialization, parental engagement, and feedback management for policy improvement. The success of online PPDB depends not only on technological systems but also on citizen support as primary actors in public policy.

A key point in NPS is creating policies relevant to local contexts. In the zoning system, this synchronization is evident in how Gorontalo City adjusts zoning rules to local geographic characteristics and community needs, such as considering densely populated areas or regions with limited schools.

This approach indicates that the online PPDB implementation in Gorontalo City is not merely an administrative policy but a reflection of NPS principles, aiming to establish an inclusive, fair, and public-interest-oriented education system.

Research by Setiyanti [8] aligns with this perspective, suggesting that the zoning-based PPDB system can address educational quality disparities between urban and suburban areas. However, challenges arise in areas like Temanggung, which has six public junior high schools. Findings in Gorontalo echo Setiyanti's view that the zoning system holds great potential for reducing educational inequality but requires implementation adjustments. Factors like school distribution, technological infrastructure, and community understanding are pivotal to its success and should be addressed through collaborative efforts between the government, schools, and the community.

In conclusion, the online PPDB services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City have successfully achieved most of their main objectives. The system has met student admission targets based on school capacity and prioritized admissions by residential location. Additionally, the implementation of the zoning system has contributed to reducing educational disparities and ensuring an efficient registration process. However, challenges such as inaccurate student domicile data in the system remain. Improvements in data management systems and service quality are necessary to enhance effectiveness and meet community expectations comprehensively.

B. Integration in the Effectiveness of Online New Student Admission (PPDB) Services through the Zoning System at the Junior High School Level in Gorontalo City

The second dimension of effectiveness indicators can be measured through **integration** [5]. Integration relates to how well various elements within a program are interconnected and function harmoniously. Adaptation, on the other hand, reflects the program's ability to adjust to changing conditions and societal needs [9]. Integration is the organization's ability to conduct socialization, reach consensus, and establish communication with other organizations [6].

Integration emphasizes the importance of coordination and alignment of functions or subsystems within an organization to achieve shared objectives. This means integration is the process of aligning various elements in an organization to create operational harmony for achieving common goals [5]. In complex environments such as technology-based public services, integration is essential to unify data and information, make efficient decisions, improve cross-functional and unit coordination for smooth processes, and support adaptation to environmental changes through collaboration and innovation.

The findings from the study show that the online PPDB platform through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City demonstrates the implementation of integration principles through the following that The PPDB system successfully

integrates registration data centrally, allowing all stakeholders—including schools, the Gorontalo City Education Office, and the community—to access the same real-time information. This reflects vertical integration, where data flows seamlessly between operational levels (schools) and strategic levels (the Gorontalo City Education Office). Automated selection based on criteria such as zoning and age enhances operational efficiency, aligning with horizontal integration principles that coordinate functions or units within the system. Automation reduces human error, a key objective of integration to improve decision-making quality. Collaboration between the Education Office, schools, and PT Telkom Indonesia showcases integration not only at the technical level but also across sectors. This cooperation reflects the need for adaptation and synergy in dynamic environments. Real-time data updates on school capacity, the number of applicants, and admission status improve transparency. This transparency, enabled by well-integrated technology systems and data management, strengthens public accountability in service delivery.

Despite these successes, the research identified several challenges that require attention for better integration: This highlights the need for improved internal coordination to ensure all stakeholders can effectively utilize the system. External integration, or alignment between the system and its users (parents and the community), has not been fully achieved. Suboptimal technological infrastructure hampers full integration and operational efficiency.

To overcome these obstacles and maximize the benefits of integration, the following steps are suggested: Improve network capacity to handle high traffic during peak registration periods. The Gorontalo City Education Office should provide ongoing training for school operators and teachers and enhance public outreach to improve understanding and participation. Collaborate with PT Telkom Indonesia to develop data correction features to improve system flexibility and responsiveness to user needs. Through these approaches, more comprehensive integration can be achieved, supporting the objectives of transparent, efficient, and inclusive online PPDB services through the zoning system in Gorontalo City.

The NPS approach, which redefines the government's role as a facilitator and service provider, emphasizes the importance of coalitions and partnerships among the government, private sector, and civil society. This framework strongly aligns with the findings on integration in the online PPDB system in Gorontalo City. The local government acts as a facilitator, creating systems to ensure transparent, efficient, and inclusive registration processes. Beyond providing technological infrastructure, the government facilitates coordination among schools, the community, and relevant sectors to ensure effective implementation of the zoning policy. Collaboration with private entities such as PT Telkom Indonesia supports the system's functionality, particularly in software development, internet infrastructure, and technical support. Civil society, including school committees, community leaders, and parents, plays a crucial role in providing feedback and support for the policy. Their participation ensures the system aligns with local needs and fosters public trust in the PPDB process.

Zoning represents a consensus between the government and the community to address disparities in educational access. The study highlights that the zoning-based PPDB system has succeeded in promoting equitable access for students from diverse regions, reflecting collective efforts to meet shared needs.

Research findings on the integration of the online PPDB system align with effectiveness concepts by Tika [10], which emphasize success in achieving objectives through optimal resource utilization. The findings demonstrate that the integration of the online PPDB system in Gorontalo City reflects effectiveness, as evidenced by centralized data integration, transparency, and accelerated selection processes. However, to achieve higher effectiveness, additional resources such as training and technological infrastructure improvements are necessary to address existing challenges. Similarly, organizational effectiveness, as defined by Silalahi [11], highlights achieving goals through optimal and quality implementation. The integration within Gorontalo's online PPDB system has largely fulfilled its primary objectives through well-organized and effective execution, consistent with this concept. Addressing technical obstacles, improving public literacy, and optimizing human resource training are critical for achieving even higher levels of organizational effectiveness.

In conclusion, the online PPDB platform through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has successfully integrated data centrally and enabled real-time updates and automated selection processes. The system's success is supported by collaboration between the Gorontalo City Education Office, schools, and PT Telkom Indonesia as the technology provider. However, challenges such as limited training for school operators and teachers, insufficient public understanding of zoning rules, and technical issues like network infrastructure capacity still need to be addressed. By overcoming these barriers, the system can further enhance its effectiveness in delivering transparent, efficient, and inclusive educational services.

C. Adaptation in the Effectiveness of Online New Student Admission (PPDB) Services through the Zoning System at the Junior High School Level in Gorontalo City

The third dimension of effectiveness indicators can be assessed through **adaptation** [5]. Adaptation reflects a program's ability to adjust to changing conditions and societal needs [9]. It involves the capacity to modify standard operating procedures when environmental conditions change. Adaptation encompasses enhancing capabilities, facilities, and infrastructure [6]. Adaptation emphasizes the importance of an organization or system's ability to adjust to external and internal environmental changes to remain relevant and effective. It includes flexibility in policies, systems, and operations to meet evolving needs and address emerging challenges [5]. Findings from the study on the zoning-based online PPDB system in Gorontalo City can be analyzed within this context.

Flexibility is central to a system's ability to respond to change [5]. The PPDB system in Gorontalo City was designed to ensure equal opportunities for all students, including those from underprivileged families or with limited access to technology. This operational flexibility reflects the system's adaptation to the social realities of Gorontalo City, where zoning policies are applied to ensure equitable access to education. This demonstrates the system's responsiveness to the needs of marginalized communities, adapting to changes in the social environment.

The use of diverse communication channels, such as social media, official websites, and public announcements by the Education Office and schools, highlights the system's adaptive response to varied communication patterns within the community. Effective communication adaptation ensures organizational relevance to its audience [5]. The use of multiple media formats reflects structural adaptation, wherein organizations adjust their work methods based on user patterns and needs.

The high level of responsiveness displayed by PPDB implementers, including openness to feedback, indicates the system's ability to handle challenges like technical issues or data errors. This dynamic adaptation demonstrates the system's capacity to improvise and improve operations when faced with obstacles [5]. By incorporating feedback loops, implementers continuously refine the system.

Challenges such as unstable internet access and limited community understanding of technological applications indicate that adaptation efforts are not yet fully optimal. Technical barriers point to the need for strengthened network infrastructure, while social barriers highlight the importance of improving digital literacy among the population.

Recommendations for Enhancing Adaptation: Introduce offline registration options for areas in Gorontalo City with limited internet access. Collaborate with PT Telkom Indonesia to develop user-friendly applications that accommodate low technological literacy. Enhance adaptive communication by increasing socialization efforts through direct outreach or video tutorials to improve public understanding of the PPDB process. Address technical challenges by increasing internet network capacity, particularly in school environments, and provide additional training for PPDB operators and the community to ensure comprehensive understanding of the system.

The zoning-based online PPDB system in Gorontalo City has been designed with sufficient flexibility, reflecting the principles of adaptation in operational and communication aspects. However, technical and social challenges indicate that further improvements are needed to achieve optimal adaptation. By enhancing infrastructure, improving communication, and increasing technological literacy, the PPDB system can continue to evolve and align with community needs.

The NPS approach, which emphasizes enrichment and continuous adaptation [12], is highly relevant to the findings on adaptation in the PPDB system in Gorontalo City. The implementation of online PPDB represents the government's adaptation to technological advancements and modern societal needs. This system replaces manual processes with technology-based approaches, aligning with the NPS principle of enriching government services through innovation.

Zoning policies in Gorontalo City were designed considering local characteristics, such as the geographic distribution of schools, population density, and infrastructure access. This demonstrates how a general policy is adapted to meet specific community needs. Feedback from the community regarding challenges like internet access limitations or lack of technical understanding was addressed by the local government through system improvements and support services, such as parental assistance.

The collaboration between the government, schools, and the private sector reflects the NPS principle of co-creation and inclusivity in service delivery. For instance, technical support from local technology providers ensures the system is widely accessible. The government's provision of affirmative measures for vulnerable groups, such as specialized admission pathways, ensures that the zoning system accommodates individual needs while upholding collective interests.

The PPDB system's adaptation to technology enhances transparency in the registration process, allowing citizens to monitor selection processes directly. This aligns with the NPS commitment to accountability and better public services. Through consultation and evaluation, the local government adjusts the zoning policy to ensure greater acceptance by the community, reflecting NPS values of flexibility and empowerment.

The findings align with the concept of public service effectiveness by Ponto et al. [13], where the zoning-based PPDB system in Gorontalo City demonstrates effectiveness in achieving its primary goals. However, to ensure long-term effectiveness, further efforts are needed to address technical, social, and operational challenges to achieve comprehensive goal attainment. This is consistent with Campbell [14], who emphasizes achieving goals comprehensively, reflecting how the Gorontalo City Education Office executes its duties to fulfill the objectives of the PPDB service.

The findings also support research by Warsita [1], which shows that online PPDB systems provide faster, more orderly, transparent, accountable, effective, and efficient services to the community. Online systems ensure adherence to established rules, reduce risks of manipulation, and promote digital literacy among the population. However, challenges in Gorontalo City highlight the need for improvements in infrastructure and digital literacy to support more inclusive implementation.

The zoning-based online PPDB system in Gorontalo City has been designed flexibly to meet community needs. The Education Office and schools provide accessible communication channels, such as social media, official PPDB websites, and public announcements. The system demonstrates good responsiveness in addressing technical challenges during the registration process. Online PPDB operators are open to feedback from various stakeholders, including parents, students, and schools, to improve services. However, challenges such as unstable internet access in schools and limited public understanding of the system remain. By addressing these barriers, the system can continue to adapt and provide equitable and efficient services for the community.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings and discussion, it can be concluded that the achievement of objectives in the online New Student Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has not been effective due to challenges such as inaccurate student domicile data within the system and dissatisfaction among the community (parents and prospective students) with the online PPDB services. The integration in the online New Student Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has also not been effective, as it still faces obstacles such as limited training for school operators and teachers, insufficient understanding among the community, particularly parents, regarding zoning rules, and technical issues related to the capacity of the network infrastructure that needs to be improved. The adaptation in the online New Student Admission (PPDB) services through the zoning system at the junior high school level in Gorontalo City has not been effective either, as it continues to face challenges such as unstable internet accessibility in schools.

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